

Demagnetization Detection, Misdiagnosis and Impact in Permanent Magnet Generators

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Abstract—Permanent magnet generators are key electrical machines in remote renewables power applications. Their ability to operate in direct-drive condition together with high efficiency and modularity are just some of the reasons. However, they may experience faults that if undetected will evolve. It is therefore crucial to detect faults reliably to avoid catastrophic failures. This paper deals with the detection of demagnetization in direct-drive permanent magnet generators. The paper focuses on the application of various diagnostic methods and compares their detection capabilities. Moreover, the authors will investigate cases of false negative diagnostic alarms that lead to misdiagnosis.

Keywords—*demagnetization, fault diagnosis, permanent magnet generators, renewables*

I. INTRODUCTION

Remote renewables, such as wave, wind and tidal energy harvesting pose specific requirements. Due to the difficult access to the generating systems, it is necessary to adopt devices that require the minimum amount of maintenance possible [1]. This is the reason behind the advancement of the permanent magnet (PM) generators, and especially the direct drive ones for such applications [2].

The combination of inherent manufacturing tolerances and stresses during operation leads to the formation of early faults, following the degradation of the machine components [3]. PM machines may suffer from either eccentricity faults, demagnetization, or stator inter-turn faults [4]. Other faults of a more mechanical nature are bearing faults and misalignment.

Detecting faults at an incipient stage is of paramount importance in the field of electrical machines. This is because the faults will evolve in severity and may lead to a catastrophic failure if not promptly detected [3]. Moreover, one fault may be the starting point for the appearance of a different fault and the two faults can manifest together, thus accelerating the failure's evolution. One such example is the strong relation between the appearance of an inter-turn fault and the consequent demagnetization of the rotor [5]-[6].

The demagnetization fault is related to PM machines. Permanent magnets can be permanently demagnetized under two different conditions. The first one is the thermal overstress [7] and the second the overload of the machine [8]. Regarding the former, the B-H characteristic of permanent magnets is

affected by the operating temperature. If a critical threshold is exceeded, then the remanence of the magnets drops, and the magnets lose a portion of the magnetization capabilities. Regarding the latter, overloading of the machine will draw high current and create an opposing magnetic field strong enough to cause permanent demagnetization in the permanent magnets.

The demagnetization fault may evolve in severity as follows: Considering a fixed load, the machine will operate under elevated current to produce the same power. This means higher Joule losses and higher operating temperature that may cause more demagnetization until a critical current level is reached.

Due to its significance, the demagnetization fault and its detection has seen significant interest and research efforts inside the diagnostics community. Past works have utilized the MCSA (Motor Current Signature Analysis) [9], flux monitoring [10] and other methods to detect the fault [11].

While widely used, MCSA has acknowledged limitations in detecting mechanical defects related to bearing, eccentricity, or load, with vibration analysis considered more reliable for these issues. This method, is based on processing the current signal's frequency spectrum, proves effective in identifying various faults [12].

The analysis of airgap or stray flux emerges as a potent diagnostic method, offering direct insights into the machine's radial or axial flux asymmetry induced by fault-related anomalies. Airgap flux monitoring, utilizing components like radial leakage flux and axial leakage flux, proves superior in detecting faults such as shorted field winding turns, rotor conductor issues and airgap eccentricity, displaying heightened sensitivity compared to vibration analysis or Motor Current Signature Analysis (MCSA) [3].

In most works, the authors treat non-uniform demagnetization, as the uniform one cannot be detected by spectral analysis because it does not create relevant harmonics in the monitored signals. It is worth mentioning that recent research has shown the trailing edge demagnetization effect and methods have been proposed to detect such a fault in PM motors [13]. In PM generators with high number of poles, it has been shown that the stator current harmonics relevant to the fault are directly dependent on the combination between poles and stator concentrated windings [14]-[15]. Moreover,

cases of possible misdiagnosis have been experimentally proven [10]. Recent works deal with the detection of the fault under transient machine operation [16]. Finally, it is worth mentioning that a significant amount of work has focused on the discrimination between the eccentricity and demagnetization faults due to them producing similar harmonics in the stator current spectra [17]-[19].

This paper is dealing with C-GEN [20], direct-drive, PM generators for renewables. Using extensive Finite Element simulations, the impact of non-uniform demagnetization is examined, while different methods are assessed as to their diagnostic capability and fault severity sensitivity. Additionally, the authors study cases of non-uniform demagnetization that may lead to false negative diagnostic alarms when the stator current analysis is applied. If these faults are not identified, the diagnostic result will incorrectly indicate that the machine is in good condition, even though it is experiencing demagnetization issues. It is crucial to understand that when one magnet is found to be demagnetized, it does not imply that the demagnetization is uniform across all magnets. A defect in a single magnet can occur independently. NdFeB magnets are especially susceptible to irreversible demagnetization due to their poor thermal properties, low resistance to corrosion in humid conditions, and weak mechanical strength, which can lead to deterioration through corrosion, cracking, or the loss of small fragments from the edges [21]. Finally, the generators' overall performance, including an analysis of losses, efficiency, and electromagnetic behavior under healthy and faulty conditions, is presented, aiming to increase our understanding of the underlying mechanisms that act on the machine under fault and may lead to prognostic conclusions.

II. MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Aiming for a reliable electromagnetic analysis, a model of a radial flux C-GEN generator has been built and its performance is compared to the experimental results obtained from the real device. A cross section of the model is shown in Fig. 1, depicting the magnetic flux distribution under healthy conditions. The nominal characteristics of the generator are shown in Table I. Moreover, the comparative results of the FEA model and the experimental testing are presented in Table II together with the percentile difference between the two. The simulated machine describes the real one with satisfying accuracy.

Fig. 1. FEA model of the C-GEN generator and magnetic flux distribution.

TABLE I. PM GENERATOR NOMINAL CHARACTERISTICS

Rated power	21.5 kW
Rated speed	100 rpm
Stator	Coreless
Frequency	26.67
Pole pairs	16
Stator Coils	24 x single concentrated
Stator coil turns	205
Magnet material	N42

TABLE II. FEA MODEL VS REAL GENERATOR COMPARISON

Variable	FEA	Experiment	Difference
Phase Voltage (V)	292.4	306.7	4.67%
Phase Current (A)	16.71	17.41	4.02%
Torque (Nm)	1494	1575	5.14%
Output Power (kW)	14.65	15.4	4.87%
Input Power (kW)	15.64	16.5	5.21%
Efficiency (%)	93.6	93.3	-0.32%

III. MCSA RESULTS

The generator has been simulated to operate under various faulty conditions. Firstly, only one magnet has been demagnetized by two different severity levels (25% and 50%). Then, two non-adjacent magnets were demagnetized. The two magnets are apart by one bipolar pitch. The two faulty magnets have been set to have equal severities (both 25% and 50%) as well as different (one 25% and the other 50%). The reason is that it has been shown in past works [14] that demagnetized magnets at specific locations on the rotor may lead to false negative diagnostic alarms when the MCSA is applied.

The MCSA results are shown in Fig. 2 for all the studied cases. Due to equations (1)-(3) [14], the expected harmonics, indicative of demagnetization, are located at $f_s - \frac{f_s}{2}$ and $2f_s$ for this machine topology.

$$\begin{cases} f_{\text{dmg1}} = \left(n \pm \frac{2^{\delta} \cdot \varepsilon}{p} \right) f_s, \text{ produced due to coils at } \frac{\pi}{2} & (1) \\ f_{\text{3ph_null}} = \frac{3\gamma_{ph} \cdot \lambda'}{p} f_s, \text{ cancelled due to 3 - phases} & (2) \\ f_{\text{dmg2}} = \left(n \pm \frac{3\kappa}{p} \right) f_s, \text{ produced due to 3x coils} & (3) \end{cases}$$

The respective amplitudes are presented in Table III. The results prove that the amplitudes of the two signatures increase monotonically with the increase of the fault severity, in the case of one demagnetized magnet (DM). Despite that, it is to be noted that the right one at double the fundamental frequency does not reach a significant final amplitude and in a real case there is the chance of this harmonic being lost on the noise floor. The left sideband is characterized by a significant amplitude and is prominent for diagnosis. Contrary to the above, when two magnets are demagnetized by equal amounts and they are located apart by one bipolar pitch, the magnetic asymmetry is not expressed in the form of the left strong sideband anymore. This harmonic has similar

amplitude to the healthy machine. Additionally, the right sideband increases however its amplitude is meaningful when the severity level becomes important.

Fig. 2. MCSA results for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: a) 1 demagnetized magnet by 25%, b) 1 demagnetized magnet by 50%, c) 2 non-adjacent demagnetized magnets by 25%, d) 2 non-adjacent demagnetized magnets by 50% and e) one demagnetized magnet by 25% and a non-adjacent by 50%.

TABLE III. MCSA - FAULT SIGNATURES AMPLITUDES

Machine condition	$f_s - f_s/2$	$2f_s$
Healthy	-119.32 dB	-119.79 dB
1 DM – 25%	-58.05 dB	-87.54 dB
1 DM – 50%	-51.06 dB	-80.34 dB
2 DM – 25%	-118.72 dB	-80.38 dB
2 DM – 50%	-118.41 dB	-73.23 dB
2 DM – 25% & 50%	-57.92 dB	-76.20 dB

IV. ELECTROMAGNETIC ANALYSIS

The phase winding consists of 8 coils divided in two in-series subgroups, each consisting of 4 coils in parallel. When the demagnetization fault appears, the coils receive different electromotive forces from the rotor at every instant. However, the coil voltage must be the same due to the parallel connection. This means that the parallel loops will carry circulating currents. The best way to demonstrate their impact is to calculate the current difference between the healthy and faulty state at every time. The differences of the 4 parallel coil currents when the machine experiences a demagnetized magnet (25% fault severity) are shown in Fig. 3. The circulating currents have a phase shift over time which depends on the rotor speed.

Fig. 3. Waveforms of the current difference over time in four parallel coils of phase A.

Magnetic asymmetry is expected to impact the generator's losses and efficiency. This has also been investigated here, and interesting outcomes have been generated. Tables IV-V present the analysis results. Firstly, the impact of the fault on the power efficiency is shown in the last column of both

tables. The efficiency is more negatively affected by the demagnetization fault when the load drops (3-phase ohmic resistance increase). This is attributed to the circulating currents. Since the generator has the same speed in both loading cases, the electromotive force is the same. Therefore, the induced circulating currents have similar losses in both cases, however the total losses are different due to the different stator currents required by the different loads. As a result, the less the load, the stronger the fault's impact on efficiency. This is supported by Fig. 4, depicting a coil's current difference under three different loads. The circulating current appears to be the same.

TABLE IV. LOSSES AND EFFICIENCY – RATED LOAD

Machine condition	Joule losses/input	Magnetic losses/input	Efficiency (%)
Healthy	4.01%	2.31%	93.68
1 DM – 25%	4.15%	2.37%	93.48
1 DM – 50%	4.56%	2.55%	92.90
2 DM – 25%	4.64%	2.60%	92.76
2 DM – 50%	4.26%	2.42%	93.32
2 DM – 25% & 50%	4.99%	2.77%	92.23

TABLE V. LOSSES AND EFFICIENCY – 75 % OF RATED LOAD

Machine condition	Joule losses/input	Magnetic losses/input	Efficiency (%)
Healthy	3.25%	1.90%	94.85%
1 DM – 25%	3.42%	1.98%	94.60%
1 DM – 50%	3.93%	2.20%	93.87%
2 DM – 25%	4.03%	2.27%	93.70%
2 DM – 50%	3.56%	2.05%	94.40%
2 DM – 25% & 50%	4.47%	2.48%	93.05%

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 4. Current difference, between faulty and healthy condition, of a random stator coil for the generator suffering from one demagnetized magnet by 50%, where a) 25% more resistive load, b) rated load and c) 25% less resistive load.

V. ALTERNATIVE DIAGNOSTIC APPROACHES

Since the MCSA is incapable of reliable diagnostic outcomes, alternatives should be explored in order to maximize the reliability of the fault detection strategy. In this work, two more electromagnetic variables of the generator are studied, namely, the magnetic flux and the torque.

A. Magnetic Flux Analysis

It is important to clarify that the MCSA is, in a way, a flux monitoring technique. The stator winding is the magnetic flux sensor that senses asymmetries of the magnetic field in the form of induced voltages and therefore the harmonic index of the flowing current is affected by them. However, the inherent disadvantage of MCSA is its dependence on the machine's number of poles. In other words, the spatial distribution of the winding in accordance with the magnetic poles of the machine, is the main reason behind the harmonic cancellation in many diagnostic cases. This drawback does not exist in the flux monitoring methodologies because the sensor geometry is not related to the number of magnetic poles. As a result, harmonic cancellation phenomena are absent from this procedure. Specifically, in this study flux monitoring relies on sensors mounted on the stator coils sensing the air-gap flux.

The spectral results are shown in Fig. 5. Firstly, the obvious advantage of the flux over the stator current is that due to the lack of harmonic cancellation, multiple signatures of the fault appear in the spectra. Specifically, when only one magnet is affected, harmonics of frequency $f_s \pm k \frac{f_s}{p}$, $k \in \mathbb{Z}$, appear in the faulty machine. Those harmonics' amplitudes are around -60 dB for fault severity 25% and increase by about 7 dB for 50% severity. Furthermore, when two non-adjacent magnets exist at a bipolar distance, we can see a cancellation phenomenon at frequencies $f_s \pm \frac{f_s}{2}$. Despite that, all the other signatures are present and can reveal the fault. Their amplitudes are not almost uniform as those when only one magnet is demagnetized though. The signatures follow an oscillating pattern, with progressive weakening of their amplitude close to the cancellation frequencies. Finally, when the two non-adjacent bars are faulty but by different severity levels, there is no cancellation phenomenon, however the amplitudes are also oscillating along the frequency.

Fig. 5. Flux monitoring results for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: a) 1 demagnetized magnet by 25%, b) 1 demagnetized magnet by 50%, c) 2 non-adjacent demagnetized magnets by 25%, d) 2 non-adjacent demagnetized magnets by 50% and e) one demagnetized magnet by 25% and a non-adjacent by 50%.

B. Torque Analysis

The electrical machine torque analysis for fault detection has not received a lot of attention in previous years. There are of course papers in the field [22], however in real applications torque monitoring has not been adopted, due to practical difficulties in measuring the shaft torque directly. Despite that, the electromagnetic torque spectra can be estimated via 3-phase voltage and current monitoring. So, there is non-intrusiveness, online and remote monitoring capabilities of this method.

For this purpose, the torque spectra of the studied cases are analyzed in this paragraph. The spectra are shown in Fig. 6 for all cases. The interaction of the main rotor magnetic field with the new stator fields due to the field will give rise to torque oscillations at frequencies: $f_s + \frac{f_s}{2}$ and $f_s + 2f_s$. Those correspond at approximately 40 Hz and 80 Hz in this case. Their respective amplitudes are shown in Table VI. For early faults such as a single magnet demagnetization, the amplitude increase of the first signature is higher than 40 dB. The second signature, although it increases significantly, has relatively low amplitude. The two non-adjacent demagnetized magnets influence the first signature amplitude, however, do not cancel its increase completely. When the fault severity increases (50%), then the amplitude is clearly higher than that of the healthy machine. So, the fault may be detected but its severity not.

The outcomes of the torque are strongly related to vibrations analysis. In this case, the torque is a better signal than the stator current, from a diagnostic point of view, however not ideal.

Fig. 6. Torque monitoring results for faulty cases (red) versus the healthy (black) where: a) 1 demagnetized magnet by 25%, b) 1 demagnetized magnet by 50%, c) 2 non-adjacent demagnetized magnets by 25%, d) 2 non-adjacent demagnetized magnets by 50% and e) one demagnetized magnet by 25% and a non-adjacent by 50%.

TABLE VI. TORQUE SIGNATURES' APLITUDES (DB)

Machine condition	$f_s + \frac{f_s}{2}$	$f_s + 2f_s$
Healthy	-102.66	-119.17
1 DM – 25%	-60.27	-95.06
1 DM – 50%	-56.08	-80.31
2 DM – 25%	-82.51	-87.71
2 DM – 50%	-67.62	-74.78
2 DM – 25% & 50%	-61.69	-79.51

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has investigated the impact of demagnetization on radial flux C-GEN permanent magnet generators. The results have shown MCSA's lack of reliability to detect the fault in non-adjacent cases. Moreover, the torque is better suited for detection than MCSA, while the air-gap flux monitoring proves to be the best method. Furthermore, the paper has shown that the circulating currents have a negative result on the generator efficiency and that their impact is independent from the load, therefore the efficiency suffers more at low loading conditions of the generator. Future, work should focus on the identification issues between demagnetization and other rotor faults. Finally, experimental testing is being planned to verify the FEA conclusions.

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